

EXPERIENCE ECONOMY AS AN IRRATIONAL PHILOSOPHY IN TOURIST AND HOTEL SERVICES IN TRANSFORMING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The aim of this conceptual paper is to develop recommendations for the implementation of a strategy for marketing impressions in tourism and hospitality enterprises, thereby emphasizing the importance of the role of the impressions economy in the provision of tourist and hotel services in the context of the transformation of socio-economic systems. The strengthening of the concept of impressions economy is a certain reaction to the changing conditions in the service economy. The article analyzes a new type of relationship between the brand and the consumer - marketing of impressions, as well as the conditions that contribute to the successful functioning of tourism and hospitality enterprises, thereby emphasizing the fact that there is a mass process in the consumption of hotel and tourist services and the formation of certain value positions. Analyzing the problem of the role of impressions marketing in the provision of tourist services and hotel products in the context of the transformation of socio-economic systems, it was revealed that the concept of impressions economics at the beginning of the 21st century strengthens its position, which is manifested in the limitless nature of postmodern hedonism among modern consumers of the service sector.

Keywords: Philosophy; Irrationalism; Impressions Economics; Shaping the Experience of Tourists; Transformation Socio-economic Systems.

ECONOMIA DA EXPERIÊNCIA COMO UMA FILOSOFIA IRRACIONAL NOS SERVIÇOS TURÍSTICOS E HOTELEIROS EM SISTEMAS SOCIO-ECONÔMICOS EM TRANSFORMAÇÃO

Resumo

O objetivo deste ensaio teórico é desenvolver recomendações para a implementação de uma estratégia de marketing de impressões em empresas de turismo e hotelaria, enfatizando assim a importância do papel da economia das impressões na prestação de serviços turísticos e hoteleiros no contexto da transformação dos sistemas socioeconômicos. O reforço do conceito de economia das impressões é uma certa reação à mudança das condições na economia dos serviços. O artigo analisa um novo tipo de relação entre a marca e o consumidor - marketing de impressões, bem como as condições que contribuem para o bom funcionamento das empresas de turismo e hospitalidade, enfatizando assim o fato de haver um processo de massa no consumo de serviços hoteleiros e turísticos e a formação de certas posições de valor. Analisando o problema do papel do marketing de impressões na prestação de serviços turísticos e de produtos hoteleiros no contexto da transformação dos sistemas socioeconômicos, revelou-se que o conceito de economia de impressões no início do século XXI reforça a sua posição, que se manifesta na natureza ilimitada do hedonismo pós-moderno entre os consumidores modernos do setor dos serviços.

Palavras-chave: Filosofia; Irracionalismo; Economia de Impressões; Conformação da Experiência Turística; Sistemas Sócio-Econômicos em Transformação.

LA ECONOMÍA DE LA EXPERIENCIA COMO FILOSOFÍA IRRACIONAL EN LOS SERVICIOS TURÍSTICOS Y HOTELEROS DE SISTEMAS SOCIOECONÓMICOS EN TRANSFORMACIÓN

Resumen

Este ensayo teórico se dedica a elaborar recomendaciones para la aplicación de una estrategia de comercialización de las impresiones en las empresas de turismo y hostelería, destacando así la importancia del papel de la economía de las impresiones en la prestación de servicios turísticos y hoteleros en el contexto de la transformación de los sistemas socioeconómicos. El fortalecimiento del concepto de economía de las impresiones es una cierta reacción a las condiciones cambiantes de la economía de los servicios. El artículo analiza un nuevo tipo de relación entre la marca y el consumidor - el marketing de impresiones, así como las condiciones que contribuyen al buen funcionamiento de las empresas turísticas y de hostelería, destacando así el hecho de que existe un proceso de masas en el consumo de servicios hoteleros y turísticos y la formación de determinadas posiciones de valor. Al analizar el problema del papel del marketing de las impresiones en la prestación de servicios turísticos y productos hoteleros en el contexto de la transformación de los sistemas socioeconómicos, se reveló que el concepto de economía de las impresiones a principios del siglo XXI refuerza su posición, que se manifiesta en el carácter ilimitado del hedonismo posmoderno entre los consumidores modernos del sector de los servicios.

Palabras clave: Filosofía; Irracionalismo; Economía de las impresiones; Configuración de la Experiencia Turística; Sistemas Socioeconómicos en Transformación.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In the context of the modern development of society in the first third of the 21st century, a transformation of socio-economic life is taking place, characterized by the construction of intensive socio-economic relations. It is worth noting that these changes directly affect many aspects of the life of society, as well as economic systems. In such circumstances, new opportunities for economic systems to develop and develop are opened up.

Economic systems are subject to change, transforming with man, they require constant renewal and "adjustment," since certain knowledge related to the functioning of economic systems in the future will help to better understand the systemic factors that allow determining economic processes, as well as contribute to the search for solutions to problems emerging in the socio-economic sphere.

Accumulated by modern science, including economics, the rich potential in the field of studying theoretical issues related to the study of the economy of impressions, mass postmodern hedonism in the provision of services in the field of tourism and hospitality in the context of the transformation of socio-economic systems, allows us to emphasize that issues of a methodological nature, somehow related to understanding this problem, still remain unresolved.

In the era of digital marketing, social networks and endless flow of information, it has become very difficult to attract consumer attention. Traditional communication channels (targeted advertising, billboards, advertising on radio and TV) no longer cling, today the consumer is quite sophisticated and wants to immerse himself in the process and with it new bright impressions that he could share in social media.

All this served as an incentive to create a new direction in the tourism and hospitality industry - experience marketing (Experimental Marketing). The previous stages of economic development were the raw materials (industrial) economy and the economy of goods and services.

The impressions industry is developing in the field of museum business, the functioning of theaters, libraries, circuses, restaurant business, beauty industry, tourism and hotel facilities. The economy of impressions is a new stage in the socio-economic development of society.

The purpose of this conceptual paperⁱ is to analyze the management issues of the formation and provision of hotel and tourist services in the context of the transformation of socio-economic systems, taking into account the development of impressions economics and the philosophy of irrationalism.

Additionally, we discuss and develop recommendations for the implementation of the marketing strategy of the tourism and hospitality industry in order to improve the work in terms of providing a tourist package of services and a hotel product.

2 THE RELEVANCE OF HEALTH TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN A COMMUNITY OF EXPERTS: A BRIEF REVIEW

The relevance of the creative application of the principles of impressions economics in the practice of systemic management of the development of tourist destinations in Russia in the modern conditions of growth of domestic and inbound tourism becomes obvious. According to the Danish futurist R. Jensen (2001), the modern era is characterized by the formation of a "dream society." The scientist believes that an era has come that will change the age of information.

Analyzing this problem, it is worth paying attention to the ideas of authoritative Russian scientists, such as V.L. Makarova, B.G. Kleiner (2007). These scientists believe that there are three groups of processes that contribute to the intensive development of the world economy in the 21st century: (1) globalization; 2) cognition; 3) structural transformation in post-socialist countries.

Globalization contributes to changes in the structure of the world economy. As is well known, globalization is essentially a process of not only political but also economic, cultural integration and unification. In connection with the scale of the formation of economic space, special value is gained: the exchange of information and technology, the international division of labor, political and economic relations, the popularization of certain types of national culture, intercultural dialogue in order to realize the spiritual and moral potential of a person.

Raising the issue of irrational philosophy, its role in the provision of tourist and hotel services, it should be noted that irrationalism is becoming a key element in the philosophical ideas of S. Kierkegaard, F. Nietzsche and A. Schopenhauer.

The issue of irrational in cognitive activity is closely related to the problem of rationality. Irrational is available in all spheres of culture, in any human activity, including in the tourism and hospitality industry. To exceed the expectations of traveler customers, someone needs to learn to think irrationally, that is, on the principle of emotional logic.

The philosophy of irrationalism in the modern world is becoming a kind of innovative philosophical concept. For A. Schopenhauer, as emphasized by

Manuel López (2021), empirical intuition is intellectual, since the integration of a subject and an object into knowledge also means the union of feeling and subjectivity and, thereby, is included in its causal effect.

The areas that allow modern specialists to prove their viability in terms of providing impressions, the ability to flexibly respond to changing conditions in the service economy are tourism and the hotel business.

The theoretical justification of the problem under consideration was reflected in the works of sociologists, philosophers (irrationalists, futurists), economists, marketers, art historians. For example, Gorbunov et al. (2018), analyzing, the tourism and recreational cluster as an organizational and economic mechanism for managing the formation and development of innovative potential. The uniqueness of such life models in the field of service provision is already in demand.

The culture of indigenous peoples and their heritage are of particular value to the impressions economy, as they provide them with access to the raw materials of the future. Russian scientists (2018) believe that exciting stories should be offered as goods. This contributes to the global distribution of a tourist or hotel product. The need of people for stories, in storytelling does not recognize either cultural or national frameworks.

Analyzing the problem of impressions economics, some scientists consider the field of tourism and the hospitality industry in the aspect of hedonism and "competent" marketing. A.P. Gorbunov and other followers of this idea (2021) believe that in the context of the transformation of socio-economic systems, the fundamental principle of economic development is the limitless nature of postmodern hedonism. Given the "need" of the market for emotional logic, scientists pay attention to the relevance of the concept of "competent marketing," as a result of which the guest/tourist either remains enthusiastic about the consumption of services, or becomes disappointed.

O.E. Afanasiev (2018), paying close attention to the problem of creating impressions, confidently believes that the formation of impressions does not begin from the moment of the start of entertainment, excursions, but from the first stage of the choice of travel: from the process of moving to the place of stay in destination to return. The Russian scientist is convinced that the formation of the impression economy determines the promotion of not only travel companies, but also tourist territories.

The relatively new concept of "impression economics" appeared in a modern context thanks to the book by Joseph B. Pine II, James H. Gilmore (2018), "Impression Economics: How to Turn a Purchase into an Exciting Action," in which impressions are defined as the fourth economic proposal, which is as strikingly

different from services as services from goods. The authors of the book claim that:

an open impression arises when the company purposefully uses services as a scene, and goods as a decoration in order to attract the client. Raw materials are equal, goods are material, services are intangible, and impressions are unforgettable (Pine & Gilmore, 1999, p. 4).

Pine and Gilmore (1999) believe that impression marketing is a strategy for creating unique events for brands. Impressions, according to this concept, become dominant in the buyer's mind. Receiving positive emotions during the consumption of services in the Horeca sector, the consumer, as a full participant in the event, receives invaluable experience, as he directly interacts with branded space and interactive objects. A tourist or guest gets exactly the experience that he will definitely want to share with friends online or offline.

Events can be completely different, both large thematic and chamber pop-up activations. All senses can be involved in the process, which allows you to create a connection at a deeper emotional level and increase consumer loyalty to the brand. Two main things that all customers are asking for now: the project should be interactive and necessarily "instagrammable," that is, visually spectacular.

Bolton Ruth N., Drew James H. (1991), referring to the study of the dynamics of consumer experience, found that current satisfaction indicators are strong predictors of future satisfaction indicators. This seems to suggest that satisfaction rates are quite stable over time and that there are strong transfer effects. Given this fact, in the context of the new information reality, the development of a "dream society," special attention should be paid to the emotional side of the provision of tourist and hotel services, since emoticons can initiate processes of updating consumer experience (Ruth, 1998).

Moreover, in the aspect of analyzing the active experience of impressions by traveler customers, the model of Japanese professor Noriaki Kano (2021) is interesting. The Kano model is a way to study the emotional response to product characteristics; this is a new approach to customer satisfaction modeling. This way helps you evaluate the importance of attributes over time. Kano developed the concept of "Attractive Quality Creation" and a questionnaire that helps to identify the characteristics of a product or service that arouse consumer admiration. The table below reflects the essence of the concepts under consideration and shows the logic of their interaction, taking into account the principle of cause-effect relationships (table 1).

Table 1. Cause and effect of the emergence of scientific concepts, which formed the basis for the analysis of the question of the value of applying the ideas of irrational philosophy in the provision of tourist and hotel services.

№ n/n	Authors of the scientific concept	The essence of the scientific concept	Causal basis (causality)	Investigation
1.	R. Jensen (2001)	Changing the era of "information" to the era of "dream society" in the development of the material world.	The principle of determinism is objective/necessary, natural (strictly conditioned), especially when the development of domestic tourism is intensified.	The emergence of a "dream society" in which its participants seek emotional satisfaction.
2.	V.L. Makarova, B.G. Kleiner (2007)	There are three groups of processes that contribute to globalization; 2) cognition; 3) structural transformation in post-socialist countries.	The principle of determinism is the objective formation of economic space in the context of the development of the world economy in the 21st century.	Exchange of information and technologies, popularization of certain types of national culture, intercultural dialogue in order to realize the spiritual and moral potential of man.
3.	S. Kierkegaard, F. Nietzsche and A. Schopenhauer.	Integration of philosophical ideas about the relationship between the irrational (emotional, intuitive) and rational (reasonable) in the knowledge of the individual.	The possibility (reality) of applying fundamental philosophical ideas.	Application of the principle of emotional logic, which is now degenerating into an innovative concept in its own right in the process of service delivery in tourism and the hospitality industry.
4.	A.P. Gorbunov, A.P. Kolyadin, L.A. Burnyasheva, L.Kh. Gazgireeva, O.Y. Kosenko (2018)	The idea put forward is about the uniqueness and relevance of elements of archaic culture, certain models of life of peoples.	The need and possibility (validity) of taking into account the features of the global distribution of tourist/hotel product as a raw material resource of the future.	Indigenous culture, their heritage, acts as a value to the experience economy, providing access to the raw materials of the future.
5.	A.P. Gorbunov (2021)	The idea put forward about strengthening boundless hedonism in the hospitality industry and tourism.	The principle of determinism is the objective conditions for the transformation of socio-economic systems in the 21st century.	The emergence of "competent marketing" in order to organize the consumption of services based on the principle of emotional (irrational) logic.
6.	O.E. Afanasiev (2018)	The idea put forward about the uniqueness of tourist destinations.	Necessity and possibility (validity) of taking into account the features of tourist areas with subsequent promotion.	The formation of the tourist's impressions since the choice of the place of stay.
7.	Joseph B. Pine II, James H. Gilmore (2018)	The idea put forward about marketing experiences: the need for a customer to get exciting experiences while traveling.	The principle of determinism is the objective formation of economic space in the context of the development of the world economy in the 21st century.	Organization of events that facilitate effective interaction of the consumer with the branded space and interactive objects.
8.	Bolton Ruth N., Drew James H. (1991)	The idea of the strength of emotions during the consumption of services as a stable indicator of consumer satisfaction.	The possibility (reality) of applying fundamental ideas of psychology.	The emergence of a "dream society" in which its participants seek to initiate processes for updating consumer experience.
9.	Noriaki Kano (2021)	A new approach to customer satisfaction modeling is to study the emotional response to product characteristics.	The possibility (reality) of applying fundamental ideas of psychology.	Relevance and timeliness of the concept of "Attractive Quality Creation" in the context of hedonistic motivation, which comes into conflict with the ideas of social order.

Source: own elaboration.

3 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Cognition under the new paradigm of the development of socio-economic relations acquires a special status in the provision of tourist and hotel services, because the awareness of the value of knowledge as a dominant resource contributes to sustainable economic growth.

Therefore, it can be stated with particular confidence that the modern service economy is a knowledge economy. And this knowledge is successfully implemented in the organization of the impression economy for consumers of services. Thus, during the period of economic formation in the post-modern era, knowledge is dominant in obtaining knowledge. Moreover, according to the concept of Makarov and Kleiner (2007), currently cognition is distinguished not by "passivity," but by intensity - "creative cognition connecting creation with awareness."

According to this statement, one thing is obvious: the integration of creative, "theatrical," potentially significant, creative approach in the provision of tourist services and the development of a hotel product is an indicator of the development of the new economy, the economy of service consumption. Therefore, it is necessary to clearly understand on what foundation it is necessary to build the economy of the future, how in the context of a systemic crisis not to "sink" in the expanses of hedonism in the sphere of service consumption, without forgetting the principle of emotional logic.

Spanish sociologist M. Castells and Finnish sociologist P. Himanen (2002), for example, believe that "information capitalism sets the rhythm and conditions for the development of production processes, determines the assignment, distribution and use of surplus in the form of consumption." Therefore, it can be concluded that in the context of the transformation of socio-economic systems, the modern consumer must change his consciousness, competently use the cognitive component, various technologies in different types of activities. Moreover, the cognitive component should be presented in the form of impressions.

According to the representative of the concept of noosphere economy Neverov (2010), a person in the post-modern era is becoming a driving force, a key figure in economic systems. Danish futurist Jensen (2021) believes that such a consumer, having creative thinking, a high degree of independence, a desire to receive and produce innovative ideas, products, can radically change his life. The near future, according to Neverov (2010), involves the formation of a noosphere economic system, thanks to which the trend of

economic growth and labor productivity will increase, applying scientific and technical achievements in various fields of knowledge.

To implement the concept of impressions marketing, the so-called "experience economy," the model of impressions economics is taken into account. According to this model, which was described by Pine and Gilmore (1999), the four areas of impressions (consumer experience) are most in demand, and in different areas of human life:

1) *entertainment/entertainment ("feel")*: implies passive absorption of impressions, that is, minimal activity and willingness to receive sensations are required from the consumer;

2) *training/educational ("learn"), or educational experience*: unlike entertainment, it requires the active participation of the consumer; the desire for new knowledge is a natural and integral part of a person's essence, but in order to transfer this knowledge to him or develop some kind of skills in a person, the full involvement of his mind (for intellectual education) or body (for physical development) is required;

3) *avoiding reality, or taking away from problems/escapist ("act")*: this type requires even more complete immersion from the consumer than in the two previous cases; is the opposite of entertainment, the consumer himself is responsible for the depth of impressions he will receive, that is, he himself participates in his impression.

4) *aesthetics/esthetic ("to be"), or aesthetic experience*: the simplest type of impression/experience for the consumer, is focused on the essence of the person and his desire for the beautiful; requires the consumer only to "be" and "perceive," that is, he does not need to change the environment or influence it. The components of "4E" vary in terms of active or passive participation and the degree of customer engagement.

Tourism and hotel sectors are developing areas of the economy in which the service is the leading position. Therefore, the country's economy as a whole depends on good service, providing a mass of impressions, a well-functioning service economy. And, taking into account the preferences of tourists, we need not only the correct policy of all actors involved in the sale of hotel and tourist services, but also a mechanism for providing these services to their consumers.

An important role here is played by a manager who is distinguished by his creative potential, intelligence, who knows how to interest and attract the client. According to the authoritative Russian scientists Makarov and Kleiner (2007), the services economy has undergone the following stages of cognitive evolution in its development: commensuration (antiquity, the era of proportionality); inquiry/recognition (Middle Ages, epoch of unanimity); recognition (New Time, Age of

Conformity); identification (the era of informatization); cognition (post-industrial society: the era of cognitive and individualization).

In the tourism industry there are various types of organizations that are engaged in tourism activities, strive to meet the specified requirements of the service economy - diversification. Diversification under the new paradigm of social development acts as a development strategy and a form of organization of production.

An important part of the tourist's and hotel's market functioning is its subjects - a tour operator, who is both the creator and wholesale implementer of tourist products; travel agent, retailer of tourist products; contractors - enterprises that contribute to the implementation of certain food, accommodation services, etc.; others on the tour; the consumer of services is a tourist.

The sphere of tourist and hotel services is an attraction space that allows a guest and a tourist to receive sports and recreation, medical, cultural, animation and excursion services, including special impressions, positive emotions. In modern times, the attraction system is focused on consumer entertainment. The choice of such services depends on the purpose of the tourist's journey, its orientation, climatic, natural features of a particular destiny, historical and cultural, national traditions and the religious component of the local population.

It is worth noting that diversification in the new paradigm of the development of society, economic systems, given the presence of processes arising in the global economy, leads to changes in marketing policy. In such circumstances, the primary goal of marketing is to retain existing customers, and not to find new ones. Only in this case, tourist and hotel enterprises will receive high profits.

The economic force for the enterprises of the hotel and tourism industry in the first third of the 21st century is special measures taken not only to increase sales of tourist products, but also to form the loyalty of customers already existing in tourist enterprises. Which does not seem insignificant. J. R. Walker (2021, p. 231) writes about this: "Loyalty marketing is a set of modern marketing tools that allows you to turn casual and regular consumers into loyal adherents of a product (goods and services), brand, company, brand."

The marketing concept assumes that all the company's activities should have the main goal of meeting the needs of users, since this is the best way to achieve their own goals of growth and increasing the income of the enterprise (Yankevich & Bezrukova, 2003, p.78).

Moreover, by constantly conducting marketing research and observing changes in customer

preferences, it is possible to form consumer loyalty, since such a differentiated approach allows adjusting the strategic behavior of travel agents and tourism enterprises, communication in general.

Analyzing the issue of the functioning of enterprises in the field of hospitality, we emphasize that the advantages of hotel chains are quite obvious. Kulgachev and other Russian scientists (2020), revealing the features of the functioning of hotels included in the network, believes that this strategy, even during the economic crisis (the loading of hotels of known chains even in the post-crisis period was 15-20% higher than that of other Russian hotels) turned out to be productive.

Scientists believe that a single booking system allows you to help and look for options for customers around the world and increase the load as much as possible. A single database allows you to create more convenient routes, provide information support to staff and maintain the highest quality of service.

The unified financial system helps to conduct a huge number of advertising events in foreign and local markets. Advertising plays a key role and is an important element in the development of the hospitality industry.

For hotels, another huge advantage of inclusion in the international network is the possibility of using the latest technologies and technologies, which is another factor in increasing the irrational (emotional) component of the tourist/guest. This allows you to renovate without closing hotels and worrying their guests. The use of innovative technologies will increase the emotional effect when the client consumes hotel services.

The design of the hotel certainly influences the emotions and feelings of the guest. Spolon Ana Paula (2011), analyzing the content of the material structure of hosting in urban clusters in Brazil, pays special attention to building design. The study showed that hotel design is perceived as an element of differentiation, capable of maximizing results, given the processes of restructuring modern urban spaces, which, in turn, also affects the emotional sphere of the guest.

Gorbunov and other Russian scientists (2018) argue that recognition is a huge advantage for hotels that operate under the brands of international chains. Considering the issue of emotional logic regarding the branding of hotels, it is believed that international operators make large investments in the recognition of their brands.

Each brand is a carrier of potential quality. Each brand must always provide the same and guaranteed number of services, regardless of the country of

location. This applies to room space, free Wi-Fi, the presence of a business center, etc.

Another thing is that these services can be provided in different ways, given the strategy and tactics of marketing impressions. For example, bungalows in the African savanna are in particular demand, the equipment of which is far from the standards of high-class hotels, or floating hotels (botels), in which the level of comfort may also be low. Therefore, the hotel sells not only basic and additional services combined into a hotel product, it also sells impressions, which often do not depend on the equipment of the room or the availability of dry cleaning.

A hotel room with a beautiful view can cost more (impressions fee), as the hotel provides its guests not only a comfortable room, but also the opportunity to get an unforgettable impression of a cup of coffee drunk on a balcony overlooking the ocean at sunset. This aspect should be taken into account when developing ways of advertising influence on the target audience, potential clients of the hotel enterprise, who better perceive the appeal not as a client, but as a guest.

It is also worth noting that according to the method of influencing the target audience, according to B. Schmitt (2001), irrational (emotional), rather than rational advertising that emphasizes feelings, emotions and memories, comes to the fore.

Active methods of perceiving impressions include culinary master classes, various quests, interactive museums, which are gaining popularity. Spanish scientists Berta Leidy González Valdés, Yanisley Moya Monteagudo (2021) believe that the hotel is no exception and can create "maximum humanization of the hospitality process," as well as a teaching (educational) impression, providing the opportunity to hold various forums, conferences, master classes in a specially equipped congress hall.

Another active way to get new impressions is to get away from reality, the guest of the hotel enters the impression (and not it, as in a passive type), which is why casinos in hotels are so popular. As one of the options for creating active impressions in the hotel is the rental of sports equipment, the services of an instructor in extreme sports. Resort hotels are already actively using this.

The organization of impressions in the thematic context (eastern style, the world of the wild west, village style, etc.) is very popular at present, as an example of this in the hotel business, we can cite the design of Guest House No. 17 in Rostov-on-Don, where each room is decorated in the themes of different countries and cities. A similar example can be boutique hotels, the motto of which is the creation of a warm, home and even intimate environment, taking into account the wishes of the guest. Therefore, we can say that when

developing the concept of the hotel's development, it is necessary to take into account the general principles of impressions economics.

Another active way of perceiving impressions is theatrical, when a guest, while in a hotel, does not just watch, for example, a show in a hotel restaurant, but takes an active part in it. Such immersivity immerses the client in the "living" atmosphere of the hotel. To implement this approach, resort hotels use the services of animators, arrange theatrical performances for meeting guests.

From the point of view of the economy of impressions, the price of a hotel product is determined not only by the cost of a room and additional services, but also by the guest's ability to get new positive impressions (unforgettable impressions of a cup of coffee drunk on a balcony overlooking the ocean at sunset); various paid or free souvenir products that serve as a reminder of impressions, and also allows the hotel to secure the status of a regular customer.

Taking into account the above, the following recommendations can be made for the marketing of impressions in the tourism and hospitality industry. To create an impression concentration, it is necessary to adhere to the following principles of developing a tourist product, using the best practices in Russian tourism that contribute to the creation of an irrational philosophy (impressions) during travel:

1. *Create emotional anchors* - personal moments that will remain in memory. For example, in Adygea, on one of the evenings, the tour organizers offer guests a light dinner not in a camp or restaurant, but in one of the key photo locations of the region - the Eagle Regiment rock.

2. *The most important souvenir is a photo* (therefore, it is necessary to think about tourists, how and where they can be made at the best). For example, Norway's most popular photo magnet is the Troll Tongue Rock. Every tourist wants to take such a photo. And in Yakutia they came up with their own photo magnet - a fountain of boiling water, which freezes in the cold. Guides specially wake guests, preparing simple props to take a photo at dawn, while the frost is as severe as possible.

3. *Check all the elements of the tour program on yourself, that is, in real space and time, with real tourists.* Every detail in the tour must be thought out. For example, one of the options for a group photo that guests will accurately post on social networks is a photo with the Arctic Circle stele in Chukotka. The secret of these shots is the signature of a place that immediately speaks of where the tourist was, and the mood and dynamics are a small procurement of guides.

4. *In the description of the booklet-program, promise only what will definitely be implemented 100%.*

For example, the Baikalika company uses many interesting gastro techniques in its tours. One of them is a small ritual “kiss Baikal” the guys came up with specifically for business programs. All guests are invited to “drink” homemade moonshine from small holes that are made in ice. For the first time in the tour, this ritual is used as a “dedication to icebreakers,” but then it is repeated at the request of guests every day.

5. For each activity (case, tour element) have plan B. For example, in Kislovodsk, being on an excursion, a tourist can be offered to catch trout himself to cook it on a mangale. This process takes place against the backdrop of Honey Falls - a magnificent landscape

6. At every moment of the program try to exceed the expectations of guests. For example, if tourists go on a jeep tour, the following elements may exceed their expectations if:

- the column of machines will be branded;
- there will be end-to-end communication of crews with the possibility of feedback;
- it will be possible to try personally the principle of management of the new mode of transport;
- the process of the move itself will be perceived as a new type of activity, that is, the source of the impression is an unusual transport, a picturesque road, interesting stopping places, fascinating and informative accompaniment;

- the “degree” of impressions will be increased due to the use of the reception of the “major final,” namely: the brightest events and some memorable moments must be planned at the end of the day, the program;

- during intellectual activities, use additional techniques that will make the information more interesting: a) the use of music, poetic lines (about the places where the tourist is located); b) showing videos (films shot in the place where the tourist is staying, in order to show the place that once might have looked different); c) the attention of guests to smells (food, plants) and sounds (nature, music); d) presence of tactile/kinesic sensations (animals, tissue, plants).

7. Constantly apply the storytelling of destinations as a modern technology in tourism. For example, during a trip to the Rybachy Peninsula, guides read K. Simonov’s work “Son of an Gunner” and put on the song “Farewell, Rocky Mountains” (author of the words N. Bukin, composer E. Zharkovsky), which were written about the military events taking place in these places. It is this technique of reading literary works used by the guide that causes certain emotions among the tourist.

According to the authors of the article, the components of “4P” can contribute to the activation and more effective functioning of the categories of the 4E model in the hospitality industry (table 2).

Table 2. Essence of “4P” components, which are the basis of formation of educational, aesthetic experience of tourists, their experience of entertainment and avoiding problems.

Organization	Educational experience	
Restaurant	4P components:	1. Properties (“1P”) properties. > The photo gallery, which adorns the restaurant hall, involuntarily immerses the guest in the history of his owner’s family. 2. Product presentation (“2P”). > The menu is distinguished by special dishes reflecting the local color. 3. Promotional Tools (“3P”). > The restaurant hosts a specially organized event “Wines of Kuban” to present local types of grapes and wines, differences in their taste and use. 4. People/People (“4P”). > The trained staff of the restaurant confidently tells its visitors about different varieties of wine or beer, while recommending the best choice for the ordered dish and its combination with other dishes.
Hotel accommodation		1. Properties (“1P”) properties. > In front of the hotel is a beautiful rosary. 2. Product presentation (“2P”). > The ethnic style in the interior of the hotel contains illustrated images of local legends. 3. Promotional Tools (“3P”). >The hotel booklet tells on its pages a cognitive story about an ancient ornament painted on a rare plate in the finish of the hearth. 4. People/People (“4P”). > The owner of the hotel and the city chess champion hold weekly chess tournaments with guests.
Aesthetic experience		
Restaurant	4P components:	1. Properties (“1P”) properties. > Warm light creates a relaxed and relaxing effect. 2. Product presentation (“2P”). > Colorful design of dishes in the form of colorfully made photos contributes to more frequent treatment of guests and the fulfillment of frequent orders. 3. Promotional Tools (“3P”). > Advertising focuses on exclusive dishes, which gradually contributes to an increase in the number of guests who have become gourmets of the cuisine of this restaurant. 4. People/People (“4P”). > The chef creates a special dish that corresponds to the client’s personal tastes.

Table 2 – continuing...

Hotel accommodation		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Properties ("1P") properties. > The hotel garden has private places for guests to walk. 2. Product presentation ("2P"). > Ornament on bed linen and towels, gown brings comfort and comfort to the hotel room. 3. Promotional Tools ("3P"). > Colored brochures demonstrate the elegance of the interior of the hotel. 4. People/People ("4P"). > The massage method used by an experienced masseuse in the hotel spa allows guests to relax and go to the "nirvana."
Entertainment experience		
Restaurant	4P components:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Properties ("1P") properties. > A large aquarium with its inhabitants attract the attention of restaurant visitors, as well as contribute to relaxation. 2. Product presentation ("2P"). > The menu uses appetite-inspiring snack names. 3. Promotional Tools ("3P"). > Charity events are held in the restaurant. 4. People/People ("4P"). > Guests not only observe the preparation of Italian lasagna, but can also take part in a master class on its preparation.
Hotel accommodation		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Properties ("1P") properties. > Balconies allow you to observe what is happening on the property. 2. Product presentation ("2P"). > The napkins on the table are folded in a special way and resemble animals in shape. 3. Promotional Tools ("3P"). > The information publications of the hotel contain brief information about the adventures of guests during travel. 4. People/People ("4P"). > Guests of the hotel are involved in lively conversations and events held on the property (animation, for example).
Experience in avoiding problems		
Restaurant	4P components:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Properties ("1P") properties. > The interior design of the family restaurant resembles village cuisine. 2. Product presentation ("2P"). > The ornament of dishes resembling the Greek style is used in a themed restaurant. 3. Promotional Tools ("3P"). > The paper of the advertising materials of the coffee shop is impregnated with coffee aroma. 4. People/People ("4P"). > Employees of the restaurant of Spanish cuisine emphasize the correct pronunciation of the names of dishes in the menu (paella, for example).
Hotel accommodation		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Properties ("1P") properties. > The architectural design in the form of a castle for a themed hotel in the Gothic style allows the guest to forget. 2. Product presentation ("2P"). > The interior of the hotel restaurant is given a special charm by ancient lace dining textiles in an ethnic style. 3. Promotional Tools ("3P"). > Advertising of the hotel attaches particular importance to the opportunity to get away from real reality, in particular from life problems. 4. People/People ("4P"). > The staff of the themed hotel has authentic clothes in order to immerse the guest in another atmosphere.

Source: own elaboration.

As additional activities, you can use certain methods of attracting potential consumers of services who want to plunge into a "dream society," while wanting to gain experience in the future.

In the work of tourist and hotel enterprises, you can use the SOLOMA method proposed and developed by the authors of this article. SOLOMA is a mixture of topical, innovative, author's and interesting in one territory, a mixture of popularity and exclusivity, as well as democracy and elitism. This method can be presented in more detail as follows (table 3).

These events will turn the pages on social networks not only into a "profitable" place, but also create a kind of "scene" for showing some events/events of the hotel, in which a guest from the first minutes of acquaintance with her would want to participate in her life, stay there for the night.

Table 3. SOLOMA: Element interaction matrix.

SO	is a social space on various platforms (Facebook, VKontakte, Odnoklassniki), working with reviews in TripAdvisor, booking (booking.com) or other online resource;
LO	local marketing ("covered marketing"), which is based on the map of the hotel and takes into account everything that is next to it. It is necessary to assess how it is possible to convert, convert the capabilities of this territory into profit;
MA	marketing, in its broader sense, with promotions, using communication channels with regular guests, using interactive modern resources, partner marketing itself, which can be developed.

Source: own elaboration.

To carry out business communications on social networks, increasing the so-called likes on the page with posted information about their tourist or hotel enterprise, since the loyalty (return of interest in a

particular enterprise) of consumers of tourism and hospitality services must not only be preserved, but also increased.

According to the authors of the article, publications on social networks should be posted at least twice a week. This approach will allow you to “immerse” the guest in the atmosphere of marketing impressions, if you skillfully talk about what is happening in the hotel, what events are being held there.

Considering that advertising of the hotel enterprise is becoming more and more not “commodity” (describing the components of the hotel product), and “prestigious” (showing what advantages the guest will have and what new impressions he can get by settling in the hotel), it is necessary to submit information about a hotel or tourist enterprise, applying the formula of success of sales via the Internet 30 + 30 + 30 + 10, attracting guests and tourists by any means - through the yandex director, gugl advords, avito, SEO, lead magnets, etc. It looks like this in more detail (table 4).

Table 4 – Formula for the success of hotel sales.

30%	30%	30%	10%
The first 30% relate directly to the PR campaign (lidogeneration): it is necessary to post information about your enterprise, holding some holidays, using various actions, etc. The second 30% should be devoted to describing the environment of a particular service enterprise, that is, what happens around a certain hotel or tourist enterprise, what happens in the city where this enterprise operates (for example, parking opened), thereby presenting a “new look” at a certain hotel. After all, in this city, for example, there is someone's favorite hotel. Do not overload the page with design (“usability”) and it is necessary to formulate a clear call to action, since the guest must understand where he got and what he is required to do.	The last 30% should be devoted to the individuality of your enterprise, that is, to dedicate a guest or tourist to what is happening in this hotel or in this tourist company, which is discussed on a social page (for example, to “reposition” some information that interests the guest: rest guests with animals, etc.). For Facebook, for example, there is a special IT resource with which you can connect the letter mechanism (paying, of course, for it).	Such an online towing tool, which, as a rule, is available on any site of an advanced hotel in this regard, will be associated with Property Management Sistem, in particular with the work of the hotel room management system, but this function will already be implemented from the Facebook social network page. It can be customized by color, logo, name. As a result, this will look the best way, since contact with the guest is established, has feedback.	And finally, the remaining 10% are responsible for the right place and the right time. An accidental combination of circumstances related to the decision to buy a hotel product or a package of tourist services should also be taken into account.

Source: own elaboration.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Thus, due to changes in the needs and behavior of the tourist, the marketing of impressions is now beginning to strengthen its position. The modern consumer chooses not so much a function, and not even a brand, but the sensations and impressions that he will receive from using the product. The experience of impressions at the time of consumption of tourist and hotel services is presented as a philosophy of irrationalism, since the market functions according to the laws of emotional logic. Therefore, a tourist or hotel product should contain characteristics that can surprise the client, make him admire and convey his impression to others.

Such an algorithm for implementing the concept of the Japanese scientist Noriaki Kano (2021) - “creating an attractive quality” in the form of providing

experience of impressions - is seen by the authors of this article as the most relevant and promising.

The economy of impressions can become a good tool for promoting a hotel product and a tourist package of services, if you skillfully combine many ways to attract traveler customers.

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Table. CRediT author statement.

Term	Definition	Autor 1	Autor 2	Autor 3
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+		
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+		
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+		
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs			+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data		+	
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	+

Term	Definition	Autor 1	Autor 2	Autor 3
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+		
Writing – Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+		
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages		+	
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+		
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+		
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

Processo Editorial / Editorial Process / Proceso Editorial
 Editor Chefe / Editor-in-chief / Editor Jefe: PhD Thiago D. Pimentel (UFJF).
 Recebido / Received / Recibido: 02.04.2022; Revisado / Revised / Revisado: 09.07.2022 – 31.08.2022; Aprovado / Approved /
 Apobado: 21.09.2022; Publicado / Published / Publicado: 04.10.2022.
 Seção revisada às cegas por pares / Double-blind peer review section / Sesión revisada por pares ciegos.

ⁱ In this article, the authors relied on general scientific research methods - expert assessments, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, a systemic approach, analogy and classification, economic

methods for assessing the quality of management of the field of hospitality and tourism (Mazaro, 2011).